

Molar volume, viscosity and conductance studies of ascorbic acid in water, 0.01 M aqueous sodium chloride and dextrose + 0.01 M aqueous sodium chloride

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Abstract : Molar volume, viscosity and conductance of ascorbic acid in water, 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and 2, 4 and 6 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride solutions have been evaluated from density, viscosity and conductance data respectively at temperatures 303.15, 308.15, 313.15 and 318.15 K. The solute-solvent interactions for ascorbic acid in water, 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and 2, 4 and 6 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride have been inferred from ϕ_v^0 , B -coefficient of Jones-Dole equation and Λ_m^0 values. The structure making/breaking behaviour of ascorbic acid is inferred from the sign of $[\partial^2 \phi_v^0 / \partial T^2]_p$, dB/dT , transition state theory i.e. free energy contribution per mole of solute ($\Delta\mu_2$) and free energy contribution per mole of solvent ($\Delta\mu_1$) values and temperature coefficient of Walden product i.e. $d(\Lambda_m^0 \eta_0)/dT$. It has been found from viscosity and conductance studies that ascorbic acid behaves as structure-breaker in water, 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and 2, 4 and 6 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride solutions. The energy of activation for ascorbic acid in different systems has also been calculated from conductance and viscosity data.

Keywords : Molar volume, viscosity, conductance, ascorbic acid-water-sodium chloride-dextrose system.

Introduction

The study of apparent molar volumes of electrolytes at infinite dilution, B parameter of Jones-Dole equation and their dependence on temperature, transition state theory, molar conductance at infinite dilution and Walden product studies can furnish useful information on the nature of solute-solvent interactions. The behaviour of electrolytes in aqueous carbohydrates and carbohydrates containing small quantity of ions which are present in body fluids has recently been subject of interest¹⁻⁷. Increasing concern over the essentialness of ascorbic acid in living organism has led to increase research activity to identify the importance of component in the living organism. All animals either make it, eat it or die from scurvy due to lack of it. Ascorbic acid helps to build and maintain tissues and strengthen immune system. It protects from heart diseases and cancer. Vitamin C deficiency symptoms include tiredness, muscle weakness, joint and muscle aches and bleeding gums. Overdoses generally nontoxic, but it may cause diarrhea, gas or stomach upset. The reco-

mmended dietary allowance for vitamin C in nonsmoking adults is 75 mg per day for women and 90 mg per day for men. For smokers the RDAs are 110 mg per day for women and 125 mg per day for men. Ascorbic acid and its sodium, potassium and calcium salts are commonly used as antioxidant food additives. The study of ascorbic acid in water, 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and 2, 4 and 6 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride at 303.15, 308.15, 313.15 and 318.15 K temperatures was carried out to understand the nature of solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions by measuring the density, viscosity and molar conductance of their solutions.

Experimental

Water used for solutions had specific conductance in the range of $0.1-1.0 \times 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$. Ascorbic acid, sodium chloride and dextrose (AnalaR) were dried over anhydrous calcium chloride for more than 48 h and used as such. All the solutions were prepared by weight and

conversion of molality to molarity was done by using the standard expression⁸. The concentration range of ascorbic acid in water, 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and 2, 4 and 6 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride solutions was 0.01 to 0.12 m. The density was measured with the help of DSA (Density and Sound Analyser) 5000, Antor Paar, GmbH, Garz, Austria. Viscosity was determined with the help of capillary type Viscometer⁹. The conductance was measured with the help of calibrated Digital conductivity meter, CM 180, Elico Limited. All measurements were made in a water bath maintained at 30, 35, 40, 45 °C (±0.05).

Results and discussion

The apparent molar volume of ascorbic acid in water, 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and 2, 4 and 6 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride solutions have been calculated from density data (Table 1) by using eq. (1),

$$\phi_v = \frac{M_2}{d^0} - \frac{1000(d - d^0)}{mdd^0} \quad (1)$$

where d^0 is the density of solvent, d is the density of solution, m is the molality of solution and M_2 is the molecular weight of ascorbic acid. Errors in ϕ_v were calculated from eq. (2),

$$\Delta\phi_v = (2\Delta d/d^2) (1000/m + M_2) \quad (2)$$

Eq. (2) assumes error to be associated with the density of solution (d) and solvent (d^0). Moreover, errors associated with determination of solution concentration are not the limiting factor while calculating the apparent molar volumes. The error in apparent molar volume as derived from eq. (2) was estimated to range from $\pm 0.06 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at 0.01 m concentration to $\pm 0.10 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at 0.12 m concentration. The densities of various solutions of ascorbic acid in water, 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and 2, 4 and 6 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride solutions obey Root's equation and justify the use of Masson's eq. (3) for the estimation of the limiting apparent molar volume,

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + S_v \sqrt{C} \quad (3)$$

where ϕ_v^0 and S_v are calculated from the intercept and slope from the extrapolation of the plots of ϕ_v versus

Table 1. Densities, apparent molar volumes, relative viscosities and molar conductance of ascorbic acid in water, 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and different compositions of dextrose (2, 4 and 6%) in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride solutions at different temperatures

Concentration $C \times 10^2$ (mol L ⁻¹)	Density d (g cm ⁻³)	Apparent molar volume ϕ_v (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	Relative viscosity η/η_0	Molar conductance Λ_m (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)
Water				
Temp. = 303.15 K	$d_0 = 0.995647$		$\eta_0 = 0.79730 \text{ cP}$	
0.9946	0.996355	105.71	1.00831	351.90
1.9871	0.997046	106.34	1.01222	312.01
3.9656	0.998395	107.38	1.01828	252.17
5.9356	0.999715	108.11	1.02329	212.28
7.8967	1.001000	108.85	1.02771	177.29
9.8492	1.002270	109.39	1.03182	145.19
11.7927	1.003502	110.03	1.03562	122.11
Temp. = 308.15 K	$d_0 = 0.994060$		$\eta_0 = 0.71900 \text{ cP}$	
0.9930	0.994751	107.18	1.00778	372.61
1.9837	0.995427	107.86	1.01157	332.68
3.9591	0.996749	108.86	1.01754	272.79
5.9256	0.998045	109.53	1.02253	226.14
7.8835	0.999318	110.09	1.02704	187.73
9.8326	1.000576	110.58	1.03116	156.62
11.7726	1.001784	111.18	1.03515	131.66
Temp. = 313.15 K	$d_0 = 0.992240$		$\eta_0 = 0.65260 \text{ cP}$	
0.9912	0.992919	108.47	1.00709	393.47

Table-1 (contd.)

1.9802	0.993587	108.95	1.01063	353.50
3.9518	0.994901	109.64	1.01622	291.01
5.9147	0.996194	110.13	1.02107	243.46
7.8688	0.997461	110.63	1.02537	202.06
9.8143	0.998718	110.99	1.02940	165.06
11.7511	0.999959	111.31	1.03327	138.71
Temp. = 318.15 K	$d_0 = 0.990250$		$\eta_0 = 0.59720$ cP	
0.9892	0.990921	109.36	1.00656	424.59
1.9762	0.990921	109.85	1.00998	384.58
3.9437	0.992881	110.49	1.01552	316.96
5.9026	0.994159	110.99	1.02031	264.29
7.8527	0.995421	111.37	1.02462	220.31
9.7941	0.996660	111.77	1.02882	178.68
11.7268	0.997887	112.10	1.03268	150.08
0.01 m Aqueous sodium chloride				
Temp. = 303.15 K	$d_0 = 0.995904$		$\eta_0 = 0.80171$ cP	
0.9948	0.996607	105.90	1.00804	442.28
1.9876	0.997292	106.73	1.01190	402.50
3.9666	0.998627	107.92	1.01789	347.91
5.9368	0.999929	108.78	1.02287	308.25
7.8982	1.001192	109.63	1.02736	273.48
9.8507	1.002419	110.44	1.03146	245.67
11.7943	1.003635	111.04	1.03533	221.29
Temp. = 308.15 K	$d_0 = 0.994229$		$\eta_0 = 0.72001$ cP	
0.9932	0.994924	106.77	1.00756	473.23
1.9842	0.995601	107.60	1.01127	428.38
3.9598	0.996923	108.72	1.01703	373.76
5.9266	0.998208	109.62	1.02190	332.40
7.8846	0.999459	110.43	1.02620	296.78
9.8337	1.000691	111.06	1.03030	266.43
11.7739	1.001898	111.64	1.03416	238.66
Temp. = 313.15 K	$d_0 = 0.992109$		$\eta_0 = 0.65592$ cP	
0.9911	0.992798	107.46	1.00677	514.60
1.9799	0.993470	108.25	1.01029	469.71
3.9513	0.994781	109.37	1.01592	412.52
5.9138	0.996058	110.22	1.02091	368.63
7.8675	0.997302	111.00	1.02525	327.93
9.8123	0.998516	111.72	1.02937	297.58
11.7483	0.999716	112.27	1.03340	270.68
Temp. = 318.15 K	$d_0 = 0.987973$		$\eta_0 = 0.59819$ cP	
0.9869	0.988651	108.74	1.00633	537.03
1.9717	0.989312	109.54	1.00972	491.97
3.9347	0.990601	110.67	1.01541	426.97
5.8889	0.991854	111.57	1.02024	378.68
7.8343	0.993089	112.18	1.02481	338.26
9.7708	0.994290	112.84	1.02904	306.01
11.6983	0.995461	113.49	1.03327	274.40

2% Dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride				
Temp. = 303.15 K	$d_0 = 1.003404$		$\eta_0 = 0.84209$ cP	
1.0023	1.011169	109.01	1.00790	419.03
2.0024	1.013022	109.76	1.01170	384.54
3.9958	1.016585	110.86	1.01766	335.35
5.9802	1.020036	111.66	1.02261	299.32
7.9555	1.023313	112.36	1.02698	266.48
9.9045	1.026552	113.53	1.03114	236.86
11.8785	1.029701	113.53	1.03502	213.83
Temp. = 308.15 K	$d_0 = 1.001716$		$\eta_0 = 0.75510$ cP	
1.0006	1.002376	109.98	1.00727	439.73
1.9990	1.003021	110.66	1.01093	400.20
3.9890	1.004280	111.66	1.01683	348.46
5.9699	1.005509	112.40	1.02186	308.21
7.9418	1.006712	113.03	1.02638	275.76
9.9045	1.007891	113.59	1.03057	244.33
11.8579	1.009047	114.11	1.03467	221.79
Temp. = 313.15 K	$d_0 = 0.999503$		$\eta_0 = 0.68441$ cP	
0.9984	1.000159	110.50	1.00705	470.75
1.9946	1.000800	111.16	1.01066	431.17
3.9802	1.002053	112.12	1.01638	374.36
5.9567	1.003275	112.86	1.02129	329.04
7.9242	1.004476	113.43	1.02575	295.30
9.8824	1.005651	113.98	1.02998	260.06
11.8316	1.006803	114.49	1.03400	233.27
Temp. = 318.15 K	$d_0 = 0.997102$		$\eta_0 = 0.62312$ cP	
0.9960	1.011938	111.69	1.00657	491.97
1.9897	1.012553	112.33	1.01006	447.29
3.9705	1.013761	113.24	1.01579	387.86
5.9421	1.014937	113.96	1.02076	343.31
7.9046	1.016091	114.51	1.02527	304.89
9.8579	1.017229	115.05	1.02957	267.80
11.8020	1.018339	115.55	1.03378	239.79
4% Dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride				
Temp. = 303.15 K	$d_0 = 1.011308$		$\eta_0 = 0.88652$ cP	
1.0102	1.011938	112.49	1.00698	395.98
2.0180	1.012553	113.16	1.01054	361.74
4.0267	1.013761	113.92	1.01623	317.88
6.0259	1.014937	114.61	1.02112	283.77
8.0158	1.016091	115.16	1.02557	254.50
9.9962	1.017229	115.59	1.02968	227.09
11.9671	1.018339	116.06	1.03375	201.38
Temp. = 308.15 K	$d_0 = 1.009603$		$\eta_0 = 0.79371$ cP	
1.0084	1.010221	113.75	1.00626	416.48
2.0146	1.010825	114.37	1.00967	382.22
4.0197	1.012010	115.14	1.01507	333.36

Table-1 (contd.)

6.0154	1.013165	115.80	1.01987	295.91
8.0016	1.014297	116.35	1.02425	261.20
9.9783	1.015409	116.82	1.02843	234.51
11.9455	1.016502	117.25	1.03244	206.77
Temp. = 313.15 K	$d_0 = 1.007705$		$\eta_0 = 0.70101$ cP	
1.0065	1.008315	114.64	1.00585	437.14
2.0107	1.008912	115.21	1.00901	397.86
4.0121	1.010081	116.04	1.01431	343.96
6.0039	1.011221	116.67	1.01894	304.80
7.9862	1.012335	117.25	1.02327	266.71
9.9590	1.013438	117.66	1.02742	237.98
11.9223	1.014522	118.04	1.03127	209.69
Tempe. = 318.15 K	$d_0 = 1.005628$		$d_0 = 0.65150$ cP	
1.0045	1.006226	115.94	1.00527	457.96
2.0066	1.006814	116.37	1.00832	418.63
4.0037	1.007971	116.95	1.01359	359.67
5.9913	1.009107	117.40	1.01827	315.46
7.9695	1.010224	117.80	1.02276	274.80
9.9382	1.011329	118.10	1.02694	245.52
11.8975	1.012415	118.42	1.03094	217.59
6% Dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride				
Temp. = 303.15 K	$d_0 = 1.018638$		$\eta_0 = 0.93521$ cP	
1.074	1.019210	117.72	1.00670	353.84
2.0323	1.019772	118.13	1.01014	324.74
4.0550	1.020878	118.68	1.01574	281.14
6.0677	1.021963	119.11	1.02048	248.86
8.0705	1.023032	119.46	1.02494	219.32
10.0636	1.024082	119.80	1.02911	200.72
12.0469	1.025123	120.06	1.03311	175.98
Temp. = 308.15 K	$d_0 = 1.016809$		$\eta_0 = 0.83679$ cP	
1.0156	1.017373	118.60	1.00612	393.86
2.0287	1.017928	118.97	1.00940	364.76
4.0476	1.019022	119.46	1.01481	318.71
6.0566	1.020098	119.81	1.01961	283.99
8.0558	1.021159	120.11	1.02398	256.96
10.0451	1.022207	120.37	1.02807	232.95
12.0247	1.023240	120.62	1.03210	210.40
Temp. = 313.15 K	$d_0 = 1.011508$		$\eta_0 = 0.75380$ cP	
1.0103	1.012069	119.28	1.00571	415.72
2.0181	1.012621	119.63	1.00890	381.54
4.0265	1.013710	120.07	1.01419	332.80
6.0250	1.014779	120.46	1.01889	298.75
8.0138	1.015834	120.76	1.02331	264.55
9.9927	1.016873	121.05	1.02747	238.17
11.9620	1.017901	121.29	1.03145	214.01

Table-1 (contd.)

Temp. = 318.15 K	$d_0 = 1.010344$		$\eta_0 = 0.68892$ cP	
1.0091	1.010892	120.56	1.00493	426.11
2.0158	1.011434	120.80	1.00790	391.91
4.0217	1.012504	121.16	1.01308	338.17
6.0178	1.013559	121.45	1.01788	304.10
8.0040	1.014601	121.68	1.02230	268.61
9.9805	1.015631	121.89	1.02653	239.47
11.9473	1.016652	122.07	1.03080	215.95

\sqrt{C} . The values of limiting apparent molar volume and slopes S_v are recorded in Table 2. The slope S_v in Masson's equation may be attributed to be as a measure of ion-ion or solute-solute interactions¹⁰⁻¹², low and positive values accounts for weak solute-solute interactions in water, 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and 2, 4 and 6 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride solutions. There is a decrease in inter ionic interactions with increase in temperature for ascorbic acid in water, 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and 2, 4 and 6 wt. % of dextrose, which may be due to more solvation of solute ions with rise in temperature.

The ϕ_v^0 is a measure of solute-solvent interactions¹³. The ϕ_v^0 values for ascorbic acid in water are lower than ϕ_v^0 values for ascorbic acid in 2, 4 and 6 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride solutions shows that solute-solvent interactions are less in water than in 2, 4 and 6 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride solutions. This may be due to predominance of structure breaking effect¹⁴ of sodium chloride over structure making effect¹⁵ of dextrose in water system. The ϕ_v^0 values for ascorbic acid in water, 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and 2, 4 and 6 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride solutions increases with increase in temperature and it may be due to decrease in hydrogen bonding between water molecules with increase in temperature, thus making more free water molecules available for solvation of solute ions and hence solute-solvent interactions increase with increase in temperature.

The temperature dependence of ϕ_v^0 for ascorbic acid in water, 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and 2, 4 and 6 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride

solutions can be expressed as :

$$\phi_v^0 = 99.68 + 0.939T - 0.0009T^2 \quad (4)$$

(For ascorbic acid in water)

$$\phi_v^0 = -1072.73 + 7.44T - 0.0118T^2 \quad (5)$$

(For ascorbic acid in 0.01 m sodium chloride)

$$\phi_v^0 = -1133.97 + 7.45T - 0.0111T^2 \quad (6)$$

(For ascorbic acid in 2% dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride)

$$\phi_v^0 = -638.58 + 4.65T - 0.0072T^2 \quad (7)$$

(For ascorbic acid in 4% dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride)

$$\phi_v^0 = -906.91 + 4.97T - 0.0078T^2 \quad (8)$$

(For ascorbic acid in 6% dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride)

Here the temperature T is expressed in Kelvin (K).

The limiting apparent molar expansibility, $\phi_E^0 = (\partial \phi_v^0 / \partial T)_p$, calculated for ascorbic acid from eqs. (4), (5), (6), (7) and (8) are given in Table 2. The values of ϕ_E^0 decreases with increase in temperature for ascorbic acid in water, 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and 2, 4 and 6 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride solutions indicates the absence of "caging effect"¹⁶ and its behavior is just like common electrolytes^{17,18}. The structure making/breaking capacity of ascorbic acid may be interpreted with the help of Hepler's reasoning¹⁹, i.e. on the basis of sign of $(\partial^2 \phi_v^0 / \partial T^2)_p$. It has been shown from general thermodynamic eq. (9),

$$(\partial \bar{C}_p^0 / \partial P)_T = -T(\partial^2 \phi_v^0 / \partial T^2)_p \quad (9)$$

where \bar{C}_p^0 is the partial molar heat capacity at infinite

Table 2. Limiting apparent molar volume ϕ_v^0 , S_v , apparent molar expansibility (ϕ_E^0) and excess molar volume ($\Delta\phi_v^0$) of ascorbic acid in water, 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and in different compositions of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride at different temperatures

Solvent	Temp. (T) (K)	ϕ_v^0 (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	S_v (cm ³ L ^{1/2} mol ^{-3/2})	ϕ_E^0 (cm ³ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	$\Delta\phi_v^0 = (\phi_v^0(A) - \phi_v^0(B))$ (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)
Water	303.15	103.88	0.177	0.416	-
Water	308.15	105.61	0.160	0.408	-
Water	313.15	107.30	0.117	0.399	-
Water	318.15	108.27	0.111	0.391	-
0.01 m Aq. NaCl	303.15	103.74	0.211	0.414	-
0.01 m Aq. NaCl	308.15	104.76	0.200	0.298	-
0.01 m Aq. NaCl	313.15	105.45	0.198	0.182	-
0.01 m Aq. NaCl	318.15	106.8201	0.193	0.066	-
2% Dextrose	303.15	107.1609	0.185	0.341	3.28
2% Dextrose	308.15	108.2825	0.169	0.231	2.67
2% Dextrose	313.15	108.8511	0.163	0.121	1.55
2% Dextrose	318.15	110.1070	0.157	0.011	1.84
4% Dextrose	303.15	111.0645	0.144	0.349	7.18
4% Dextrose	308.15	112.3281	0.142	0.378	6.72
4% Dextrose	313.15	113.2318	0.140	0.207	5.93
4% Dextrose	318.15	114.9353	0.101	0.136	6.67
6% Dextrose	303.15	116.7617	0.095	0.298	12.88
6% Dextrose	308.15	117.7997	0.081	0.221	12.19
6% Dextrose	313.15	118.4486	0.082	0.144	11.15
6% Dextrose	318.15	119.9239	0.062	0.067	11.65

dilution. From eq. (9), it is clear that structure making electrolytes should have a positive value of $(\partial^2 \phi_v^0 / \partial T^2)_p$ and structure breaking electrolytes should have negative value of $(\partial^2 \phi_v^0 / \partial T^2)_p$. For ascorbic acid in water, 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and 2, 4 and 6 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride solutions, the sign of $(\partial^2 \phi_v^0 / \partial T^2)_p$ has been found negative, which suggests that it acts as structure-breaker in water, 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and 2, 4 and 6 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride solutions. The limiting excess molar volume of ascorbic acid for different compositions of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride have been estimated from eq. (10),

$$\Delta \phi_v^0 (\text{excess}) = \phi_v^0 (A) - \phi_v^0 (B) \quad (10)$$

where $\phi_v^0 (A)$ is the limiting apparent molar volume of ascorbic acid in different compositions of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and $\phi_v^0 (B)$ is the limiting apparent molar volume of ascorbic acid in water. The

positive values of excess molar volume of ascorbic acid in different compositions of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride are obtained (Table 2) and it is attributed to increase in solute-solvent interactions at infinite dilution.

Viscosity studies :

The viscosity data (Table 1) has been analyzed on the basis of Jones-Dole equation²⁰,

$$\eta_s / \eta_0 = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC \quad (11)$$

where η_s and η_0 are viscosities of solution and solvent respectively, C is the molar concentration and A and B are constants. The values of A and B have been determined from the intercept and slope of linear plots of $(\eta_s / \eta_0 - 1) / \sqrt{C}$ versus \sqrt{C} . The values of A and B of different solutions are recorded in Table 3.

Parameter A of Jones-Dole equation represents the contribution from solute-solute interactions²¹. The values

Table 3. Values of parameters of Jones-Dole equation, limiting molar conductance, Λ_m^0 and Walden product for ascorbic acid in water, 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and different compositions of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride at different temperatures

Solvent	Temp. (<i>T</i>) (K)	<i>A</i> (L mol ⁻¹) ^{1/2}	<i>B</i> (L mol ⁻¹)	Λ_m^0 (Ω^{-1} cm ² mol ⁻¹)	$\Lambda_m^0 \eta_0$ (Ω^{-1} cm ² mol ⁻¹ poise)
Water	303.15	7.492	0.084	444.79	3.54
Water	308.15	6.817	0.100	472.49	3.40
Water	313.15	6.061	0.106	501.34	3.27
Water	318.15	5.399	0.121	543.29	3.24
0.01 m Aq. NaCl	303.15	7.155	0.091	530.81	4.26
0.01 m Aq. NaCl	308.15	6.640	0.099	565.30	4.07
0.01 m Aq. NaCl	313.15	5.617	0.120	612.59	4.02
0.01 m Aq. NaCl	318.15	5.004	0.137	643.40	3.85
2% Dextrose	303.15	6.965	0.093	503.78	4.24
2% Dextrose	308.15	6.130	0.115	527.64	3.98
2% Dextrose	313.15	5.905	0.115	568.75	3.89
2% Dextrose	318.15	5.264	0.132	594.33	3.70
4% Dextrose	303.15	5.798	0.114	474.72	4.21
4% Dextrose	308.15	4.974	0.127	503.45	3.99
4% Dextrose	313.15	4.488	0.132	529.84	3.71
4% Dextrose	318.15	3.733	0.152	557.74	3.63
6% Dextrose	303.15	5.441	0.118	426.67	3.99
6% Dextrose	308.15	4.766	0.129	469.91	3.93
6% Dextrose	313.15	4.276	0.139	498.53	3.75
6% Dextrose	318.15	3.262	0.163	513.14	3.53

of *A*, shows that ion-ion interactions for ascorbic acid in water, 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and 2, 4 and 6 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride solutions decrease with increase in temperature, which may be due to more solvation of solute ions.

The *B* parameter which measures the structure making/breaking capacity of an electrolyte in a solution also contain a contribution from structural effects and is responsible for solute-solvent interactions in a solvent²². It has been emphasized by a number of workers that dB/dT is more important criteria²³ for determining solute-solvent interactions. Viscosity study of a number of electrolytes has shown that structure-maker will have negative dB/dT and structure-breaker will have positive dB/dT . The temperature effect on *B* coefficient for ascorbic acid in water, 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and 2, 4 and 6 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride solutions shows a positive sign of dB/dT and thus behaves as structure-breaker in water, 0.01 m aqueous so-

dium chloride and 2, 4 and 6 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride solutions. The sample plot of *B* versus *T* for ascorbic acid in 6 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride solution is shown in Fig. 1.

The effect of temperature on the viscosity is given by eq. (12),

$$\eta = Ae^{E_\eta/RT} \quad (12)$$

where *A* is a constant and E_η is the activation energy for the viscous flow²⁴ and other symbols have their usual significances. The values of E_η for ascorbic acid in water, 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and 2, 4 and 6 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride solutions were calculated from the slope of the linear plots of $\log \eta$ versus $1/T$, and are given in Table 4.

Viscosity data has also been analysed on the basis of transition state theory of relative viscosity of electrolytic solutions as suggested by Feakins *et al.*^{25,26}. The values of $\Delta\mu_1^0$ (free energy of activation per mole of solvent)

Fig. 1. Plot of B vs T for ascorbic acid in 6% dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride at different temperatures

Table 4. Values of E_η and E_A for ascorbic acid in different compositions of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride

% Composition of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride	E_η (kJ mol ⁻¹)	E_A (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	0.04 m	
0	16.06	10.11
2	16.50	8.15
4	16.95	6.47
6	16.53	9.64
	0.06 m	
0	15.83	11.58
2	15.74	7.64
4	16.99	5.57
6	16.52	10.51
	0.08 m	
0	15.83	11.85
2	16.52	7.58
4	17.00	4.03
6	16.57	10.29

Table-4 (contd.)

	0.10 m	
0	15.39	12.37
2	16.52	6.91
4	16.99	3.99
6	16.50	8.92
	0.12 m	
0	15.61	12.40
2	16.28	6.37
4	16.92	3.97
6	16.51	10.21

and $\Delta\mu_2^\circ$ (free energy of activation per mole of solute) were calculated by using the following relations :

$$\Delta\mu_1^\circ = RT \ln (\eta_0 V_1^\circ / hN) \quad (13)$$

$$\Delta\mu_2^\circ = \Delta\mu_1^\circ + RT/V_1^\circ [1000B - (V_1^\circ - \phi_1^\circ)] \quad (14)$$

where R , h and N are gas constant, Plank constant and Avogadro's number respectively, T is absolute temperature and V_1° is partial molar volume of solvent. The values of V_1° , $\Delta\mu_1^\circ$ and $\Delta\mu_2^\circ$ are recorded in Table 5. In the

Table 5. Values of V_1° , $\Delta\mu_1^\circ$ and $\Delta\mu_2^\circ$ for ascorbic acid in water, 0.01 M aqueous sodium chloride and in different compositions of dextrose in 0.01 M aqueous sodium chloride at different temperatures

Solvent	Temp. (T) (K)	V_1° (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta\mu_1^\circ$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta\mu_2^\circ$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)
Water	303.15	18.08	61.28	84.97
Water	308.15	18.11	62.00	88.49
Water	313.15	18.11	62.75	90.82
Water	318.15	18.18	63.53	94.24
0.01 m Aq. NaCl	303.15	18.08	61.29	85.91
0.01 m Aq. NaCl	308.15	18.11	62.01	87.93
0.01 m Aq. NaCl	313.15	18.15	62.77	92.56
0.01 m Aq. NaCl	318.15	18.23	63.54	96.29
2% Dextrose	303.15	18.23	61.44	86.55
2% Dextrose	308.15	18.26	62.15	90.85
2% Dextrose	313.15	18.30	62.91	92.19
2% Dextrose	318.15	18.34	63.67	95.97
4% Dextrose	303.15	18.38	61.59	89.94
4% Dextrose	308.15	18.41	62.29	93.07
4% Dextrose	313.15	18.44	62.99	95.04
4% Dextrose	318.15	18.48	63.83	99.39
6% Dextrose	303.15	18.53	61.74	91.10
6% Dextrose	308.15	18.56	62.45	93.97
6% Dextrose	313.15	18.66	63.21	96.51
6% Dextrose	318.15	18.68	63.98	101.31

earlier prediction it suggested that for structure maker normally $\Delta\mu_1^0 > \Delta\mu_2^0$ and for breaker $\Delta\mu_1^0 < \Delta\mu_2^0$ ²⁵⁻²⁷. From the Table 5 it is found that $\Delta\mu_1^0 < \Delta\mu_2^0$ for ascorbic acid in water, 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and 2, 4 and 6 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride solutions. It suggests that ascorbic acid behaves as structure-breaker in water, 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and 2, 4 and 6 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride solutions. This may be due to increase in interactions of solute ions by the solvent molecules as a result of weakening of forces among solvent molecules at transition state.

Conductance studies :

The limiting molar conductance Λ_m^0 for ascorbic acid in water, 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and 2, 4 and 6 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride solutions was obtained by extrapolating the linear plots of Λ_m (Table 1) versus \sqrt{C} to zero concentration. The limiting molar conductance values for ascorbic acid in water, 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and 2, 4 and 6 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride solutions at 303.15, 308.15, 313.15 and 318.15 K temperatures are recorded in Table 3, which show that limiting molar conductance increases with increase in temperature, which may be due to increase in ionic mobility of free H^+ , $C_6H_7O_6^-$, Na^+ , Cl^- ions at infinite dilution.

The Walden product data ($\Lambda_m^0 \eta_0$) have been recorded in Table 3. The structure making/breaking nature of solute has been determined from temperature coefficient of Walden product i.e. $[d(\Lambda_m^0 \eta_0)/dT]$ ²⁸. The negative temperature coefficient of Walden product for ascorbic acid in water, 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and 2, 4 and 6 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride solutions indicate that ascorbic acid behaves as structure-breaker in water, 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and 2, 4 and 6 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride solutions. The sample plot of $\Lambda_m^0 \eta_0$ versus T for ascorbic acid in 4 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride is shown in Fig. 2.

The effect of temperature on conductance is given by equation²⁹,

$$\Lambda = \Lambda_0 e^{-E_A/RT} \quad (15)$$

where E_A is the activation energy for conduction and

Fig. 2. Plot of $\Lambda_m^0 \eta_0$ vs T for ascorbic acid in 4% dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride at different temperatures.

other symbols have their usual significances. The values of E_A for ascorbic acid in water, 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and 2, 4 and 6 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride solutions were calculated from the slope of the linear plots of $\log \Lambda$ versus $1/T$ and are given in Table 4.

The energy of activation for conductance, E_A should be less than energy of activation for viscous flow²⁹, E_η and it has been found that $E_A < E_\eta$ for ascorbic acid 0.04 – 0.12 m in water, 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride and 2, 4 and 6 wt. % of dextrose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride solutions.

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